

Generations and Gender Survey (Round II)

Wave 2 Questionnaire

Version 1.1

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The open competition for user modules was coordinated by Brienna Perelli-Harris (University of Southampton), Letizia Mencarini (Bocconi University), Martin Kreidl (Masaryk University), and Monika Mynarska (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University) with support from Wiktorija Bałchorek (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University). We thank everyone who submitted a module, and particularly the authors of the selected user modules included in the GGS-II Wave 2 questionnaire (see below).

Developing the GGS-II wave 2 questionnaire

The development of the GGS-II wave 2 questionnaire marks an important step in the second round of data collection of the GGS. While the GGS-II baseline questionnaire has undergone significant changes (see Gauthier et al. 2022¹ for a short history of the development of the baseline questionnaire), the follow-up questionnaire has never been reviewed. In GGS-I the two follow-up questionnaires, developed in 2006, followed the same format and content as the GGS-I baseline questionnaire with additional questions on changes in relationship and childbirth between waves. The development of the GGS-II follow-up questionnaire took a different approach. A new Questionnaire Task Force (QTF) was established to develop a new GGS-II follow-up questionnaire. The QTF was led by Monika Mynarska, with members Detlev Lück, Zsuzsanna Makay, and Laurent Toulemon. Their work was supported by Olga Grünwald from the GGP Central Coordination Team and Marta Bryzek.

The work on the follow-up questionnaire started with reviewing the GGS-II baseline questionnaire (version 3.1.0) and set out to address three major challenges. First, since the GGS is a panel survey that incorporates both retrospective and prospective elements with a strong emphasis on family and fertility issues, it was crucial to ensure that these topics remained central to the follow-up questionnaire. Second, the revision needed to allow for the inclusion of innovative elements, new items, and user-specific modules. Third, the questionnaire had to be concise and straightforward enough to be feasible for various modes, including

¹ Gauthier, A., Liefbroer, A., Ajzen, I., Aassve, A., Beets, G., Billari, F., Bühler, C., Bujard, M., Cabaço, S., Corijn, M., Désesquelles, A., Dommermuth, L., Dykstra, P., Emery, T., Fadel, L., Fokkema, T., Hansen, T., Hlebec, V., Hoem, J., ... Vikat, A. (2022). Generations and Gender Survey: Baseline Questionnaire (3.1.1). Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12724457>

Computer-Assisted Web Interviewing (CAWI) and self-administered Paper and Pencil Interviewing (PAPI).

To achieve these objectives, the GGS-II follow-up questionnaire was restructured into new thematic sections, featuring shorter segments consisting of 3–16 items each that are more cohesive than those in the GGS-II baseline questionnaire. Within each thematic segment, only the central items from the GGS-II baseline questionnaire were repeated, while problematic, complex, or less relevant items were eliminated. A major focus was placed on updating respondents' life histories, particularly regarding family-related events such as partnership history, fertility history, and migration information. For the items that were repeated from the GGS-II baseline questionnaire, the variable names were unchanged from wave 1 to ensure comparability and harmonization between the two waves. New items in wave 2 received a new variable name.

Moreover, space was allocated for several innovations from the user community. In 2023, an open competition for new content for the questionnaire took place, which received numerous submissions. A selection committee (consisting of Brienna Perelli-Harris, Letizia Mencarini, Monika Mynarska, and Martin Kreidl) evaluated these submissions, and input was also provided by the members of the GGP Consortium Board. The new modules introduced in the follow-up questionnaire include:

Singlehood (Module SING)

Dimitri Mortelmans, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Detlev Lück, Federal Institute for Population Research (BiB), Germany
Elke Claessens, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Dries Van Gasse, University of Antwerp, Belgium
Martin Bujard, Federal Institute for Population Research (BiB), Germany
Lena Frembs, University Heidelberg, Germany

Sexual Orientation (Module SEX)

Lin Rouvroye, Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (KNAW-NIDI), Netherlands
Mirjam Fischer, Goethe University, Germany
Francesco Rampazzo, University of Oxford, United Kingdom
Maaïke van der Vleuten, Stockholm University, Sweden
Fernanda Fortes De Lena, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
Christina Pao, Princeton University, United States of America
Lisa de Vries, University of Bielefeld, Germany
Yuxuan Jin, Utrecht University, Netherlands

Leaving and Returning to the Parental Home (Module PAR)

Ann Berrington, University of Southampton, United Kingdom
Brienna Perelli-Harris, University of Southampton, United Kingdom

Intensive Parenting (Module INT)

Sunnee Billingsley, Stockholm University, Sweden
Stefanie Mollborn, Stockholm University, Sweden

Livia Olah, Stockholm University, Sweden
Ann-Zofie Duvander, Stockholm University, Sweden

Global Uncertainty and Institutional Trust (Module UNC)

Gunnar Andersson, Stockholm University, Sweden
Gerda Neyer, Stockholm University, Sweden
Trude Lappegård, Oslo University, Norway
Martin Bujard, Federal Institute for Population Research (BiB), Germany

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Expand All

- *IF* (*NOT*(*search*(*ResFile*, *respid*)))
 - %CHECK[check_1_]%
- *ENDIF*
IF (*INTERVIEWER*)
 - **intid** (Interviewer ID)
Interviewer ID
STRING

ENDIF

intro (Intro)

This survey explores experiences in relationships, family, work, and other important parts of life. Your answers will help scientists understand the complexities of today's families and the reality of people at different stages of their life. The findings will also guide policymakers on improving societal issues like work-life balance, social connections, and gender equality. Your participation is voluntary, and you can skip any of the questions if you prefer. We will remove all personal identifiers from the data and ensure that your answers are only accessed by authorized users for non-commercial purposes.

[Agree to proceed](#)

DEMOGRAPHICS

DEMINT (Demographics Intro) (*Empty*)

Thank you for having agreed to participate. In (*auxFirstWaveMonthYear*); you took part in the first round of our survey. We would like to find out what has happened in your life since then and learn about your current situation. Let us start with some basic information about yourself. Please note that there are a few questions which we have asked before. We are asking them again for consistency reasons.

b1DEM01 (Gender)

What is your gender?

[Male](#)

[Female](#)

[Other / Non-binary](#)

b1DEM02 (*b1DEM02* intro) (*Empty*)

When were you born?

b1DEM02Y (Date of birth YEAR)

year

YYYY

Vertical

[NUMBER \[1900..2030\]](#)

b1DEM02M (Date of birth MONTH)

month

[January](#)

[February](#)

[March](#)

[April](#)

[May](#)

[June](#)

[July](#)

[August](#)

[September](#)

October
November
December

RESIDENCY

b2DEM17 (Residence 3 years ago) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Compared to your situation of the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), do you currently live...

At the same address

At a different address but within the same town/city/municipality

In a different town/city/municipality, in the same country

In a different country

IF (NOT(b2DEM17 = 4))

○

b2DEM04c (Place of current residence) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

In which region do you currently live?

Drenthe

Flevoland

Friesland

Gelderland

Groningen

Limburg

North Brabant

North Holland

Overijssel

South Holland

Utrecht

Zeeland

ENDIF

IF (((b2DEM17 = 2)OR(b2DEM17 = 3))OR(b2DEM17 = 4))

○

b2DEM10 (RES02_ intro) (*Empty*)

When did you start living in this accommodation?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b2DEM10Y (Date moved in YEAR) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b2DEM10Y = DontKnow)OR(b2DEM10Y = Refusal)))

▪

b2DEM10M (Date moved in MONTH) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November
December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b2DEM10Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b2DEM10Y = DontKnow))OR(b2DEM10Y = Refusal)) *[Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]*

b2DEM18 (Reason for moving) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

What was the most important reason for moving to this address?

Better housing

Better neighbourhood

For financial related reasons

For work related reasons

For education related reasons

For health related reasons

To move in with a partner

To move out of my parents' house and start living independently

For other family-related reasons

Other

b2DEM09 (Rooms [NUMBER]) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How many rooms do you have?

Exclude kitchen, bathrooms, toilets and rooms used exclusively for business, hallways and utility rooms

NUMBER [0..30]

b2DEM11 (Housing status) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Does your household own or rent this accommodation or does it come rent free?

Owner

Tenant or subtenant, paying rent

Accommodation is provided rent free

Other

ENDIF

b2DEM12 (Housing satisfaction) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How satisfied are you with your accommodation?

Please express your satisfaction on a scale of 0 to 10.

0 not at all satisfied

1

2

3

4

5 about average

6

7

8

9

10 completely satisfied

b2DEM19 (Intention to move) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to move to *another address* within the country you are currently living in within the next 3 years?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

b2DEM20 (Intention to migrate) (*Refusal*)

Do you intend to move to *another country* within the next 3 years?

- Definitely not
- Probably not
- Unsure
- Probably yes
- Definitely yes

UNION

UNIINT (Union Intro) (*Empty*)

Topics related to relationships are central in this survey. Now, we would like to ask a few questions on that.

UNIPRE (Union Changes Intro) (*Empty*)

First, we would like to find out about any changes in your partnership situation that might have happened since the last survey in ^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;.

b3UNI01 (Partner status at w1) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

At the time of the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), did you have a partner?

- Yes
- No

IF (b3UNI01 = 1)

○

b3UNI01A (Name partner W1)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the name of this partner.

You can use a pseudonym or description if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview

STRING

b3UNI02 (Lived with same partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Did you and ^b3UNI01A; live in the same household at the time of the previous survey?

- Yes
- No

IF (b3UNI02 = no)

▪

b3UNI02A (Started living with same partner) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Did you and ^b3UNI01A; start living in the same household at some later point?

- Yes
- No

ENDIF

IF (b3UNI02A = yes)

▪

b3UNI02B (UNI02b_intro) (*Empty*)

When did you and ^b3UNI01A; start living in the same household?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI02BY (Date started living with same partner YEAR) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI02BY = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI02BY = Refusal)))

- - b3UNI02BM** (Date started living with same partner MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - month
 - January
 - February
 - March
 - April
 - May
 - June
 - July
 - August
 - September
 - October
 - November
 - December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI02BY >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI02BY = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI02BY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

b3UNI03 (Legal status at w1) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Were you and ^b3UNI01A; married or did you and ^b3UNI01A; have a registered partnership at the time of the previous survey?
Yes, married
Yes, in a registered partnership
Neither

IF (b3UNI03 = 3)

- - b3UNI04** (Registered same partnership) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Did you and ^b3UNI01A; register your partnership at some later point?
Yes
No

IF (b3UNI04 = yes)

- - b3UNI04A** (UNI04a_ intro) (Empty)
When did you and ^b3UNI01A; register your partnership?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI04AY (Date same partnership registered YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI04AY = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI04AY = Refusal)))

- **b3UNI04AM** (Date same partnership registered MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - month
 - January
 - February
 - March
 - April
 - May
 - June
 - July
 - August
 - September
 - October
 - November
 - December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI04AY >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI04AY = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI04AY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((b3UNI03 = 2)OR(b3UNI03 = 3))

- **b3UNI05** (Married same partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - Did you and ^b3UNI01A; marry at some later point?
 - Yes
 - No

IF (b3UNI05 = yes)

- **b3UNI05A** (UNI05a_ intro) (Empty)
 - When did you and ^b3UNI01A; marry?
 - If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI05AY (Date married same partner YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI05AY = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI05AY = Refusal)))

- **b3UNI05AM** (Date married same partner MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - month
 - January
 - February
 - March
 - April
 - May
 - June
 - July
 - August

September
October
November
December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI05AY >=
BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI05AY =
DontKnow))OR(b3UNI05AY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a
year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

b3UNI06 (Same partner in w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you still together with ^b3UNI01A;?

Yes, we are still together

Yes, we are together again, after a break in the meantime

No

IF ((b3UNI06 = 1)OR(b3UNI06 = 2))

▪

b3UNI07 (Still together with same partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you and ^b3UNI01A; live in the same household now?

Yes

No

IF ((b3UNI07 = 2)AND(b3UNI02 = 1))

▪

b3UNI07B (UNI07b_intro) (Empty)

When did you and ^b3UNI01A; stop living in the same
household?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your
best estimate.

b3UNI07BY (Date stopped living with same partner YEAR) (DontKnow,
Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI07BY = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI07BY = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI07BM (Date stopped living with same partner
MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

```

ENDIF
CHECK: (((b3UNI07BY >=
BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI07BY =
DontKnow))OR(b3UNI07BY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a
year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]
ENDIF
ENDIF
IF (b3UNI06 = 3)
  
  b3UNI08 (How same partnership ended) (DontKnow, Refusal)
  How did your partnership with ^b3UNI01A; end?
  Broke up
  Partner passed away

  IF ((b3UNI08 = 1)OR(b3UNI08 = 2))
    
    b3UNI09 (UNI09_ ntr0) (Empty)
    When did that happen?
    If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your
    best estimate.

    b3UNI09Y (Date ended same partnership YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)
    year
    YYYY
    Vertical
    NUMBER [1900..2030]

    IF (NOT((b3UNI09Y = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI09Y = Refusal)))
      
      b3UNI09M (Date ended same partnership MONTH) (DontKnow,
      Refusal)
      month
      January
      February
      March
      April
      May
      June
      July
      August
      September
      October
      November
      December

    ENDIF
    CHECK: (((b3UNI09Y >=
    BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI09Y =
    DontKnow))OR(b3UNI09Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a
    year before your birth year
    TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)] IF ((b3UNI08 =
    1)AND((b3UNI03 = 1)OR(b3UNI05 = 1)))
      
      b3UNI10 (Divorced same partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)
      Did you and ^b3UNI01A; divorce?
      Yes
      No

```

IF (b3UNI10 = yes)

▪

b3UNI10A (UNI10a_intro) (Empty)

When did you get divorced from ^b3UNI01A;?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please
provide your best estimate.

b3UNI10AY (Date divorced same partner
YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI10AY =
DontKnow)OR(b3UNI10AY = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI10AM (Date divorced same partner
MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI10AY >=
BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI10AY =
DontKnow))OR(b3UNI10AY = Refusal)) [Not
possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

• ENDIF

LOOP I := 1 TO 20

○

IF ((I <= LastloopID)AND((b3UNI01 = 2)OR(b3UNI06 = 3)))

▪

b3UNI11_[I] (New partnership since W1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Since that time, have you had any new partner(s) with whom you
lived together as a couple in the same household or to whom you
have been married?

Yes

No

IF (b3UNI11_ = yes)

▪

b3UNI11B_[I] (Name new partner)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the name of this partner. You can use a pseudonym or description if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the interview.

b3UNI12_[I] (UNI12_intro) (Empty)

When did you and CollectionMember start living together? If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI12_Y[I] (Date started living with new partner YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI12_Y = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI12_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI12_M[I] (Date started living with new partner MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI12_Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI12_Y = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI12_Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

b3UNI13_[I] (Married new partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you and CollectionMember legally marry?

Yes

No

IF (b3UNI13_ = yes)

▪

b3UNI13A_[I] (UNI13a_intro) (Empty)

When did you and CollectionMember marry?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI13A_Y[I] (Date married new partner YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI13A_Y = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI13A_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI13A_M[I] (Date married new partner MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI13A_Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI13A_Y = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI13A_Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

IF (b3UNI13_ = 2)

▪

b3UNI14_[I] (Registered new partnership) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you and CollectionMember register your partnership?

Yes

No

IF (b3UNI14_ = yes)

▪

b3UNI14A_[I] (UNI14a_intro) (Empty)

When did you and CollectionMember register your partnership?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI14A_Y[I] (Date new partnership registered YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI14A_Y = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI14A_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI14A_M[I] (Date new partnership registered MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March
April
May
June
July
August
September
October
November
December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI14A_Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI14A_Y = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI14A_Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

b3UNI15_[I] (Still together with new partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you still together with CollectionMember?

Yes, we are still together

Yes, we are together again, after a break in the meantime

No

IF (b3UNI15_ = 3)

▪

b3LHI06_[I] (Ex-partner birthdate intro) (Empty)

When was CollectionMember born?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3LHI06_Y[I] (Ex-partner date of birth YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3LHI06_Y = DontKnow)OR(b3LHI06_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b3LHI06_M[I] (Ex-partner date of birth MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

b3UNI20_[I] (Ex-partner gender) (Refusal)

Is CollectionMember...

Male

Female

Other / Non-binary

b3UNI16_[I] (How new partnership ended) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How did your partnership with CollectionMember end?

Broke up

Partner passed away

b3UNI16A_[I] (UNI16a_intro) (Empty)

When did that happen?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI16A_Y[I] (Date new partnership ended YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI16A_Y = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI16A_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI16A_M[I] (Date new partnership ended MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI16A_Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI16A_Y = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI16A_Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)] IF ((b3UNI16_ = 1)AND(b3UNI13_ = 1))

▪

b3UNI17_[I] (Divorced new partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did you and CollectionMember divorce?

Yes

No

IF (b3UNI17_ = yes)

When did you and your partner stop living in the same household?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b3UNI18AY (Date stopped living with new partner YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b3UNI18AY = DontKnow)OR(b3UNI18AY = Refusal)))

▪

b3UNI18AM (Date stopped living with new partner MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b3UNI18AY >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b3UNI18AY = DontKnow))OR(b3UNI18AY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

• ENDIF

IF (b3UNI11_ = 2)

○

b3UNI19 (Currently not living with a partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you currently in a romantic relationship with someone you're not living with?

Yes

No

• ENDIF

IF (((b3UNI07 = 2)OR(b3UNI19 = 1))OR(b3UNI18 = 2))

○

b3DEM32A (Reasons for living apart) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you living apart because you and/or your partner want to or because circumstances prevent you from living together?

I want to live apart

We both want to live apart

Partner wants to live apart

We are constrained by circumstances

IF ((b3DEM32A = 1)OR(b3DEM32A = 2))

▪

b3DEM32B (R's reason for living apart) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Why do you personally want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.

For financial reasons
To maintain independence
Because of children
Not yet ready for living together
Other

ENDIF

IF ((b3DEM32A = 2)OR(b3DEM32A = 3))

▪

b3DEM32C (Partner's reason for living apart) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Why does your partner want to live apart? Please choose the most important reason.

For financial reasons
To maintain independence
Because of children
Not yet ready for living together
Other

ENDIF

IF (b3DEM32A = 4)

▪

b3DEM32D (Circumstances for living apart) (DontKnow, Refusal)

By which circumstances? Please choose the most important circumstances.

Work circumstances
Financial circumstances
Housing circumstances
Legal circumstances
Family circumstances
Other

ENDIF

b3DEM35 (Time to current partner's home) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your partner is living at present?

Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]

Vertical

99:99

STRING[4]

b3DEM36A (Meetings non-resident partner [FREQ]) (Empty)

How often do you meet with your partner in person?

You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.

Enter a number

NUMBER [0..365]

b3DEM36AU (Meetings non-resident partner [UNIT]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)

times a...

Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b3DEM36A = Empty)AND(b3DEM36AU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers not allowed]

b3DEM30C (Intention to start cohabiting) (Refusal)

Do you intend to start living with your current partner during the next 3 years?

Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

- **ENDIF**
IF (((b3UNI05 = 2)AND((b3UNI06 = 1)OR(b3UNI06 = 2)))OR((b3UNI13_ = 2)AND((b3UNI15_ = 1)OR(b3UNI15_ = 2))))OR(b3UNI19 = 1))
 - - **b3DEM28C** (*Intention to marry*) (*Refusal*)
Do you intend to marry your current partner during the next 3 years?
Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

- **ENDIF**
IF (((b3UNI15_ = 1)OR(b3UNI15_ = 2))OR(b3UNI19 = 1))
 - - **b3DEM22A** (*Meeting partner*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
We would like to find out more about your current partner. How did you and your current partner meet?
If multiple options apply, please select the most relevant one.
Through work
In education (school, university, college etc.)
At church or equivalent
Online dating (including dating apps)
Other online setting (e.g. social networks, online gaming, forums)
Vacation or business trip
At a bar, nightclub or dance club
Through a social organization, health club, gym or volunteer group
At a private party or social event
Through friends
Through family
Other

- **ENDIF**
IF (haspartner = yes)
 - - **b3DEM22** (*UNI29_intro*) (*Empty*)
When was your partner born?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.
 - **b3DEM22Y** (*Partner's date of birth YEAR*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]
 - IF (NOT((b3DEM22Y = DontKnow)OR(b3DEM22Y = Refusal)))
 - - **b3DEM22M** (*Partner's date of birth MONTH*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
month
January
February
March

April
May
June
July
August
September
October
November
December

ENDIF

b3DEM23 (Gender of partner) (Refusal)

Is your partner...

Male

Female

Other / Non-binary

• ENDIF

IF (((b3UNI15_ = 1)OR(b3UNI15_ = 2))OR(b3UNI19 = 1))

○

b3DEM24A (Partner born in country) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Was your partner born in 18;?

Yes

No

IF (b3DEM24A = 2)

▪

b3DEM24B (Partner's country of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In which country was he/she born?

Please type in (the first letters of) the country and then select the country from the list by clicking on it.

STRING

JOBCODER: CntFile1

ENDIF

• ENDIF

IF (haspartner = yes)

○

b3DEM37 (Relationship satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How satisfied are you with your relationship with your partner?

Please express your satisfaction on a scale of 0 to 10.

0 not at all satisfied

1

2

3

4

5 about average

6

7

8

9

10 completely satisfied

b3DEM40 (Considered break up) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Even people who get along well with their partners sometimes wonder whether their marriage or partnership will work. Over the past 12 months, have you thought about breaking up your relationship?

Yes
No

- ENDIF
IF (BUNIONS.b3UNI19 = 2)
 -

SINGLEHOOD

b4SING01 (Satisfaction with being single) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How satisfied are you with being single?

Please express your satisfaction on a scale of 0 to 10.

0 not at all satisfied

1

2

3

4

5 about average

6

7

8

9

10 completely satisfied

b4SING02 (Being single: Intro) (Empty)

The next two statements are about how you currently feel being single.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with each of them.

b4SING02A (Being single: Easier) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Being single makes life easier since I don't have to constantly consider and adapt to someone else.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING02B (Being single: Want a partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

I would like to have a partner

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING03 (Actively looking for partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you currently actively looking for a partner?

Yes

No

IF (b4SING03 = yes)

▪

b4SING04 (Dating behavior) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Where do you look for a new partner? You can select multiple answers.

SET OF Through work or education (school, university, college etc.)

At church or equivalent

Through an online dating site
Through a mobile dating app
Through online social networks, chat rooms, etc. (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, Twitter)
Vacation or business trip
At a bar, nightclub or dance club
Through a social organization, health club, gym or volunteer group
Through dating events (e.g. speed-dating, singles' parties)
At a private party or social event
Through friends
Through family
Other

ENDIF

b4SING05 (Reasons for being single: Intro) (Empty)

The next statements are about possible reasons why somebody might be single. To what extent do you agree or disagree they apply to your situation?

I am single because...

b4SING05A (Reasons for being single: Lost partner) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I recently lost my partner (due to death or a break-up)

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b4SING05B (Reasons for being single: Bad at dating) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I am not good at dating

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b4SING05C (Reasons for being single: Freedom) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I want to be free to do whatever I want

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b4SING05D (Reasons for being single: Afraid of hurt) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I am afraid I will get hurt

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b4SING05E (Reasons for being single: Nobody interested) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...nobody is interested in me as a partner

Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b4SING05F (Reasons for being single: Too picky) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I am too picky

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING05G (Reasons for being single: Health problems or disability) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I experience health problems or disability

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING05H (Reasons for being single: No time) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I don't have time to date

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING05I (Reasons for being single: Reasons for being single: Previous experience) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I've had (a) bad experience(s) in previous relationships

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING05J (Reasons for being single: Not right person) (DontKnow, Refusal)

...I haven't found the right person

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b4SING06 (Partnering intention) (Refusal)

Do you expect to have a partner within the next three years?

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure

Probably yes

Definitely yes

b4SING07 (Self-definition of being single) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Thank you, we are at the end of the questions on being single. To sum up, which of the following descriptions best describes you at the moment?

Convinced single, i.e. I do not want a committed relationship

Open to a relationship, but not actively looking

Actively looking for a partner

Incel

Relationship in the making, i.e. in the getting-to-know phase with

someone
"On-again/off again relationship", i.e. repeatedly breaking up with someone and getting back together again shortly afterwards
"Friends with benefits", i.e. a sexual relationship with a friend, but not in a steady relationship with that person
Other

ENDIF

SEXUAL ORIENTATION

b5SEX01 (Sexual orientation) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In the context of relationships, the question of sexual orientation arises.

Would you say that you are...

Heterosexual (that is, attracted to the other gender)

Lesbian or gay (that is, attracted to the same gender as you)

Bisexual or pansexual (attracted to more than one gender)

Another orientation

- IF (b5SEX01 = 4)
 - - **b5SEX01A** (Sexual orientation other) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Please describe your sexual orientation:
STRING
- ENDIF
IF (b5SEX01 = 1)
 - - **b5SEX02A** (Age of attraction to other gender) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to someone of the other gender?
If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.
NUMBER [0..100]
- ENDIF
IF (b5SEX01 = 2)
 - - **b5SEX02B** (Age of attraction to same gender) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to someone of the same gender as you?
If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.
NUMBER [0..100]
- ENDIF
IF (b5SEX01 = 3)
 - - **b5SEX02C** (Age of attraction to multiple gender) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Around which age did you first notice for yourself that you were attracted to more than one gender?
If you are unsure of the precise age, please provide your best estimate.
NUMBER [0..100]
- ENDIF
IF (((b5SEX01 = 2)OR(b5SEX01 = 3))OR(b5SEX01 = 4))
 - - **b5SEX03** (Avoidance of sexual orientation topics) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How often do you avoid talking about topics related to or otherwise indicating your sexual orientation (e.g., not talking about your significant other, changing your mannerisms)?

Never
Rarely
Half of the time
Often
Always

- ENDIF

KIDS

KIDINT (*Kid Intro*) (Empty)

The next couple of questions are about any children you might have.

b6LHI21 (*Biological children [NUMBER]*) (None, DontKnow, Refusal)

How many biological children have you had in total, including those who do not live with you or have passed away? Please include your children born via donor conception or surrogacy.

NUMBER [0..20]

b6LHI23 (*Adopted children [NUMBER]*) (None, DontKnow, Refusal)

How many legally adopted children do you have in total, including those who have passed away?

NUMBER [0..20]

- IF (hascorespartner = 1)

-

b6LHI22 (*Stepchildren*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Did your current partner have any children of their own before you got together (including those who passed away)?

Yes
No

IF (b6LHI22 = yes)

-

b6HI22A (*Stepchildren [NUMBER]*) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many children did your partner have before you got together?

NUMBER [0..20]

ENDIF

- ENDIF

IF (nkidstotal > 0)

-

b6LHI24_ (*Child name*) (Empty)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of all these children (including biological, adopted, and step-children), starting with the oldest.

You can use pseudonyms or descriptions (e.g. oldest daughter) if you prefer. This information will be deleted at the end of the survey.

Name of Child

LOOP I := 1 TO nkidstotal

-

KID00_[I] (*Child name*)

Name of Child

ENDLOOP

LOOP **I** := 1 TO nkidstotal

- - IF (((b6LHI21 > 0)AND(b6LHI23 > 0))OR((b6LHI21 > 0)AND(b6HI22A > 0)))OR((b6LHI23 > 0)AND(b6HI22A > 0)))
 - - b6LHI26_[I]** (Child type) (Refusal, NA)
Please indicate if CollectionMember is...
your biological child
an adopted child
a step child (child your current partner had before you got together)

ENDIF

b6LHI28_[I] (Gender of child) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Please indicate the gender of CollectionMember.
Male
Female
Other / Non-binary

b6LHI29_[I] (b6LHI29_ intro) (Empty)
When was CollectionMember born?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b6LHI29_Y[I] (Child date of birth YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)
year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b6LHI26_ = Step)OR((((b6LHI21 = 0)OR(b6LHI21 = none))AND((b6LHI23 = 0)OR(b6LHI23 = none)))AND(b6HI22A > 0))))

- - CHECK:** (((b6LHI29_Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b6LHI29_Y = DontKnow))OR(b6LHI29_Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

IF (NOT((b6LHI29_Y = DontKnow)OR(b6LHI29_Y = Refusal)))

- - b6LHI29_M[I]** (Child date of birth MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)
month
January
February
March
April
May
June
July
August
September
October
November
December

ENDIF

b6LHI31_[I] (Child lives in same HH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is CollectionMember currently living in the same household with you?

- Yes, always
- Yes, most of the time
- Yes, half of the time
- Yes, less than half of the time
- No, never
- Child is deceased

IF ((((((b6LHI31_ = 2)OR(b6LHI31_ = 3))OR(b6LHI31_ = 4))OR(b6LHI31_ = 5))AND(childage_ < 18))AND(childage_ = RESPONSE))

▪

b6LHI32_[I] (Child usual residency) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Where does the child stay (the rest of the time)?

- With (other) biological parent
- With (other) biological parent and his/her partner
- With (a) grandparent(s)
- With other relative(s)
- With adoptive parent(s)
- With foster parent(s)
- In a boarding school
- In an orphanage
- In a youth home
- Other

ENDIF

IF (((b6LHI31_ = 2)OR(b6LHI31_ = 3))OR(b6LHI31_ = 4))

▪

b6LHI34_[I] (Overnight stay of child [FREQ] (Ihi34)) (Empty)

How many nights does CollectionMember spend in your household on average?

b6LHI34U_[I] (Overnight stay of child [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

nights a...

- Week
- Month
- Year

CHECK: (NOT((b6LHI34_ = Empty)AND(b6LHI34U_ = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b6KID07_[I] (Child other home [MIN]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How long does it normally take to get from your home to where CollectionMember is staying for the rest of the time? Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]

Vertical
99:99

STRING[4]

ENDIF

IF ((b6LHI31_ = 5)AND(NOT(b6LHI26_ = Step)))

▪

b6LHI39A_[I] (Meeting with child [FREQ]) (Empty)

How often do you see CollectionMember in person?
You can choose to report the number of times per week,

month or year.
Enter a number

b6LHI39AU_[I] (Meeting with child [UNIT]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)

times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b6LHI39A_ = Empty)AND(b6LHI39AU_ = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b6LHI39B_[I] (Contact with child [FREQ]) (Empty)

How often do you have contact with CollectionMember by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.
Enter a number

b6LHI39BU_[I] (Contact with child [UNIT]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)

times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b6LHI39B_ = Empty)AND(b6LHI39BU_ = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed] **CHECK:** (NOT((b6LHI39B_ = RESPONSE)AND(((b6LHI39BU_ = DontKnow)OR(b6LHI39BU_ = Refusal))OR(b6LHI39BU_ = NEVER)))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b6LHI40_[I] (Child home [MIN]) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

How long does it normally take to get from your home to where CollectionMember is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM].
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

ENDLOOP

ENDIF

b6KID11 (Raised children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

We asked about your biological, adopted or step-children, but are there any other children that you raised, e.g., a child of an ex-partner or a foster child?

Yes
No

- IF (b6KID11 = yes)

-

b6KID11A (Raised children [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many are there?

NUMBER [0..20]

- ENDIF

IF (hascorespartner = yes)

-

DIVISION OF HOUSEHOLD TASKS

DIVintro (*Household Tasks Intro*) (*Empty*)

The next questions are about how you and your partner divide tasks in your household.

b7HHD11 (*Household Tasks: Intro*) (*Empty*)

Please indicate who does the following tasks in your household.

b7HHD11A (*Household Tasks: Preparing meals*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Preparing daily meals

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

b7HHD11B (*Household Tasks: Vacuuming*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Vacuum cleaning the house

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

b7HHD11C (*Household Tasks: Doing laundry*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Doing the laundry

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

b7HHD11D (*Household Tasks: Small repairs*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Doing small repairs in and around the house

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

b7HHD12 (*Household tasks satisfaction*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How satisfied are you with the division of household tasks between you and your partner?

Please express your satisfaction on a scale of 0 to 10.

0 not at all satisfied

1

2

3

4

5 about average

6

7

8

9

10 completely satisfied

IF (hascoreschildunder15 = yes)

b7HHD13 (Childcare Tasks: Intro) (Empty)

The next statements are about various tasks that have to be done when one lives together with children, even if just part of the time. Please indicate, how you and your partner divide these tasks in your household.

b7HHD13A (Childcare Tasks: Dressing) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Dressing the children or seeing that the children are properly dressed

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

Children do it themselves

b7HHD13B (Childcare Tasks: Stay with ill children) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Staying at home with the children when they are ill

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

Children do it themselves

b7HHD13C (Childcare Tasks: Playing with children) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Playing with the children and/or taking part in leisure activities with them

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

Children do it themselves

b7HHD13D (Childcare Tasks: Homework) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Helping the children with homework

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner

Always partner

Always or usually someone else

Children do it themselves

b7HHD13E (Childcare Tasks: Putting children to bed) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)

Putting the children to bed

Always me

Usually me

Equally me and partner

Usually partner
Always partner
Always or usually someone else
Children do it themselves

b7HHD14 (Childcare tasks satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How satisfied are you with the way childcare tasks are divided between you and your partner?
Please express your satisfaction on a scale from 0 to 10.
0 not at all satisfied
1
2
3
4
5 about average
6
7
8
9
10 completely satisfied

ENDIF

• ENDIF

IF (hascoreschildunder15 = yes)

○

b7HHD18 (Received regular childcare help) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with childcare from relatives or friends or other people for whom caring for children is not their (primary) occupation?
Yes
No

IF (b7HHD18 = 1)

▪

b7HHD19_ (Received regular childcare help from...) (DontKnow, Refusal, NA)
Which people have provided you with regular help with childcare?
Only include people for whom caring for children is not their primary occupation.
SET OF My mother / step-mother
My father / step-father
My partner's mother / step-mother
My partner's father / step-father
My or my partner's grandparents
My or my partner's sibling
My other child / step-child
Other relative
Friend, acquaintance, colleague, or other non-relative

b7HHD20 (Received regular childcare help [FREQ]) (Empty)
How frequently did you receive help with childcare?
You can choose to report the number of hours per week, month or year.
NUMBER [0..10000]

b7HHD20U (Received regular childcare help [UNIT]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
hours per...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b7HHD20 = Empty)AND(b7HHD20U = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers not allowed]

ENDIF

b7HHD22 (Regular institutional childcare help) (Refusal)

Do you regularly make use of any form of childcare from a day care centre, a nursery or pre-school, an after school care centre, a self-organised childcare group, a babysitter, or from some other institutional or paid arrangement?

Yes

No

IF (b7HHD22 = yes)

•

b7HHD23 (Childcare providers) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Please select all the alternatives that are regularly used.

SET OF Babysitter

Day care centre

Nursery or pre-school

After-school care-centre

Self-organised childcare group

Other institutional arrangement

ENDIF

ENDIF

b7HHD25 (Childcare help for others) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you given help with childcare to other people? If the provision of childcare is your job, please consider only the help you have given outside your professional activities.

Yes

No

• IF (b7HHD25 = yes)

○

b7HHD26_ (Childcare help for...) (DontKnow, Refusal)

To whom have you given this help? Please select all answers that apply.

SET OF My or my partner's sibling

My child/step-child

Other relative

Friend, acquaintance, colleague, or other non-relative

• ENDIF

IF ((age < 50)OR(((BUNIONS.b3DEM23 = female)AND(partnerage = RESPONSE))AND(partnerage < 50)))

○

REPRODUCTION AND FERTILITY

REPRINT (Reproduction Intro) (Empty)

The next section of the questionnaire is about sexual health and fertility. This section includes some sensitive questions. Please remember that your answers will be treated in the strictest confidence.

b8FER14 (Intention to have a child in next 3y) (Refusal)

Do you intend to have a/another child during the next three years?

Please take into account only biological children.

Definitely not

Probably not

Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes
Currently expecting a child

IF (NOT(b8FER14 = pregnant))

- - **b8FER15** (Intention to have a child at all) (Refusal)
Supposing you do not have a/another child during the next three years, do you intend to have any (more) children at all?
Definitely not
Probably not
Unsure
Probably yes
Definitely yes

IF (NOT(b8FER15 = defno))

- - **b8FER16A** (Total number of children intended) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many more children - including biological and adoptive children - do you intend to have?
Do not include existing children.
NUMBER [0..10]

ENDIF

ENDIF

b8FER16C (General ideal family size) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Generally speaking, what do you think is the ideal number of children for a family?
NUMBER [0..10]

b8FER16B (Personal ideal family size (fer16b)) (DontKnow, Refusal)
For you personally, what would be the ideal number of children you would like to have or would have liked to have had?
NUMBER [0..10]

IF (b8FER14 = 6)

- - **b8FER02** (b8FER02 intro) (Empty)
Earlier you mentioned that you or your partner were expecting a child. When is the child expected to be born?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b8FER02Y (Year due date) (DontKnow, Refusal)
year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b8FER02Y = DontKnow)OR(b8FER02Y = Refusal)))

- - **b8FER02M** (Month due date) (DontKnow, Refusal)
month
January
February
March
April
May

June
July
August
September
October
November
December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b8FER02Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b8FER02Y = DontKnow))OR(b8FER02Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

IF (NOT(b8FER14 = 6))

▪

b8FER05 (Able to have children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Some people are not physically able to have children. As far as you know, is it physically possible for you, yourself, to have a/another baby?

Definitely not

Probably not

Probably yes

Definitely yes

IF ((b8FER05 = 1)OR(b8FER05 = 2))

▪

b8FER06 (Sterilized) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you been sterilised or have you had an operation that makes it impossible for you to have a child/ more children?

Yes

No

ENDIF

IF (haspartner = yes)

▪

b8FER08 (Partner able to have children) (DontKnow, Refusal)

As far as you know, is it physically possible for your current partner to have a/another baby of their own if your partner wanted to?

Definitely not

Probably not

Probably yes

Definitely yes

IF ((b8FER08 = 1)OR(b8FER08 = 2))

▪

b8FER09 (Partner sterilized) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Has your partner ever been sterilised or had an operation that makes it impossible for them to have a child/ more children?

Yes

No

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (NOT(((BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM01 = 1)AND(((BUNIONS.b3DEM23 =

1)OR(BSEXUAL_ORIENTATION.b5SEX01 = 2))OR(haspartner = no)))OR((BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM01 = 2)AND((b8FER05 = 1)OR(b8FER06 = yes))))

▪

b8FER10A (Trying to get pregnant) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you (or your current partner) trying to get pregnant?

Yes

No

IF (b8FER10A = 1)

▪

b8FER10B (b8FER10B intro) (Empty)

When did you (or your current partner) start trying to get pregnant?

b8b8FER10BY (Year trying to get pregnant) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

NUMBER [1900..2030]

b8b8FER10BM (Month trying to get pregnant) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

CHECK: (((b8b8FER10BY >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b8b8FER10BY = DontKnow))OR(b8b8FER10BY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year
TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (NOT(((b8FER06 = yes)OR(b8FER10A = yes))OR((BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM01 = 1)AND((BUNIONS.b3DEM23 = 1)OR(BSEXUAL_ORIENTATION.b5SEX01 = 2)))))

▪

b8FER12_ (Contraceptive use) (Nothing, DontKnow, Refusal)

Are you (or your current partner) using or doing any of these things to prevent pregnancy at this time? Please name all of the things you use or do.

SET OF Condom

Pills

Intra uterine device (coil, loop)

Diaphragm/ cervical cap

Foam/cream/jelly/suppository

Injectables (e.g. Depo Provera)

Implants (e.g. Norplant)
Determining fertile days by monitoring hormone changes in urine (e.g. Persona)
Hormonal emergency contraception afterwards (morning after pill)
Withdrawal
Safe period method (rhythm)
Vaginal ring
Female condom
Other method
I'm not sexually active

ENDIF
IF (NOT((num15)IN(b8FER12_)))

b8FER13 (Intercourse in last 4 weeks) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Did you have sexual intercourse in the past 4 weeks?
Yes
No

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (NOT((BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM01 = 1)AND(((haspartner = no)OR(BUNIONS.b3DEM23 = 1))OR(BSEXUAL_ORIENTATION.b5SEX01 = 2))))

b8FER11_ (Infertility treatments) (Nothing2, DontKnow, Refusal)
Have you (or your current partner) ever done any of these things to help you get pregnant? Please select all of the things you have been doing.
SET OF Receiving medication
Methods for ascertaining timing of ovulation
In vitro fertilisation (IVF) or micro-fertilisation (ICSI)
Surgery
Artificial insemination
Consulted a physician
Other medical treatment

ENDIF

ENDIF

WELLBEING AND HEALTH

b9HEL00 (Helintro) (Empty)

We would now like to ask you some questions about your general wellbeing.

b9WEL01 (Life satisfaction) (DontKnow, Refusal)

All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

Please express your satisfaction on a scale of 0 to 10.

0 not at all satisfied

1

2

3

4

5 about average

6

7

8

9

10 completely satisfied

b9WEL09 (Loneliness: Intro) (Empty)

The next six statements are about your current experiences.

Please indicate for each of them to what extent they have applied to you recently.

b9WEL09A (Loneliness: People to lean on) (DontKnow, Refusal)

There are plenty of people I can rely on when I have problems

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL09B (Loneliness: General sense of emptiness) (DontKnow, Refusal)

I experience a general sense of emptiness

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL09C (Loneliness: Miss having people around) (DontKnow, Refusal)

I miss having people around

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL09D (Loneliness: Many people I can trust) (DontKnow, Refusal)

There are many people I can trust completely

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL09E (Loneliness: Feel rejected) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Often, I feel rejected

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL09F (Loneliness: Enough people I feel close) (DontKnow, Refusal)

There are enough people that I feel close to

Yes

More or less

No

b9WEL02 (Subjective health) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How is your health in general?

Very good

Good

Fair

Bad

Very bad

b9WEL04 (Limitation of daily activities) (DontKnow, Refusal)

For the past six months at least, to what extent have you been limited because of a health problem in activities people usually do? Would you say you have been...

Severely limited
Limited, but not severely
Not limited

b9GEN58 (Need for regular help with personal care) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Do you need regular help with personal care such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet?

Yes
No

- IF (b9GEN58 = yes)

-

b9GEN59 (Received regular personal care) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, is there any person who has helped you regularly with personal care, such as dressing, bathing or showering, eating, getting in or out of bed, using the toilet?

Yes
No

b9GEN63_ (Received regular professional care) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Over the last 12 months, have you received regular help with personal care from professional persons from the public sector or from a private organisation?

SET OF Yes, from a public sector organisation
Yes, from a private sector organisation
Yes, but not sure of organization type
No

ENDIF

HOUSEHOLD

b10HHD01B (Other HH members [NUMBER]) (None2, DontKnow, Refusal)

We have already asked you whether you have a partner or children, and whether you live with them. Apart from them, how many other persons live with you? Please also consider individuals who are household members only part of the time.

NUMBER [0..20]

- IF (b10HHD01B > 0)

-

b10HHD02_ (Name of HH member) (Empty)

To help us with guiding you through the next few questions, please provide the names of this/these other householdmember(s).

You can use pseudonyms or descriptions if you prefer and this information will be deleted at the end of the survey.

Name of Other Household Member

LOOP **I** := 1 TO b10HHD01B

-

MEM00_[I] (Name of HH member)

Name of Other Household Member

ENDLOOP

LOOP **I** := 1 TO b10HHD01B

-

b10HHD04_[I] (Relationship type to HH member) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is CollectionMember's relationship to you?
My biological mother
My biological father
My step, adoptive or foster parent
Partner's biological, step, adoptive or foster parent
My or my partner's grandparent
Foster child
My or my partner's brother or sister
Other relative of mine or of my partner
Other person

b10HHD06_[I] (b10HHD06_intro) (Empty)

What is CollectionMember's date of birth?
If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b10HHD06_Y[I] (HHmember's year of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b10HHD06_Y = DontKnow)OR(b10HHD06_Y = Refusal)))

▪

b10HHD06_M[I] (HHmember's month of birth) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month
January
February
March
April
May
June
July
August
September
October
November
December

ENDIF

ENDLOOP

ENDIF

INTERGENERATIONAL RELATIONS

b11PAR00 (Parents intro) (Empty)

The following questions are about your parents and grandparents.

IF (NOT(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.mumcores = yes))

○

b11GEN01 (Biological mother still alive) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your biological mother still alive?

Yes, she is still alive
No, she is not alive anymore

ENDIF

IF (NOT(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.dadcores = yes))

○

b11GEN02 (*Biological father still alive*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
Is your biological father still alive?
Yes, he is still alive
No, he is not alive anymore

ENDIF

IF ((b11GEN01 = 1)AND(b11GEN02 = 1))

○

b11GEN03 (*Parents live together*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
Are your biological father and mother living together?
Yes
No

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN01 = 1)

○

b11GEN15A (*Meetings with mother [FREQ]*) (*Empty*)
How often do you meet with your biological mother in person?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.
Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN15AU (*Meetings with mother [UNIT]*) (*Never, DontKnow, Refusal*)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN15A = Empty)AND(b11GEN15AU = RESPONSE))) [*Combination of answers is not allowed*]

b11GEN15B (*Contact with mother [FREQ]*) (*Empty*)
How often do you have contact with your biological mother by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.
Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN15BU (*Contact with mother [UNIT]*) (*Never, DontKnow, Refusal*)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN15B = Empty)AND(b11GEN15BU = RESPONSE))) [*Combination of answers is not allowed*] IF ((b11GEN01 = 1)AND((b11GEN02 = 2)OR(b11GEN03 = 2)))

▪

b11GEN21 (*Mother's home [MIN]*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)
How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological mother is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN02 = 1)

○

b11GEN29A (Meetings with father [FREQ]) (Empty)
How often do you meet with your biological father in person?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.
Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN29AU (Meetings with father [UNIT]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN29A = Empty)AND(b11GEN29AU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed]

b11GEN29B (Contact with father [FREQ]) (Empty)
How often do you have contact with your biological father by phone, mail, email or any other electronic means?
You can choose to report the number of times per week, month or year.
Enter a number
NUMBER [0..365]

b11GEN29BU (Contact with father [UNIT]) (Never, DontKnow, Refusal)
times a...
Week
Month
Year

CHECK: (NOT((b11GEN29B = Empty)AND(b11GEN29BU = RESPONSE))) [Combination of answers is not allowed] IF ((b11GEN02 = 1)AND((b11GEN01 = 2)OR(b11GEN03 = 2)))

▪

b11GEN35 (Father's home [MIN]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological father is living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (b11GEN03 = 1)

○

b11GEN07 (Parents' home [MIN]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How long does it normally take to get from your home to where your biological parents are living at present?
Please provide an answer in hours and minutes [HH:MM]
Vertical
99:99
STRING[4]

ENDIF

b11GEN54 (Grandparents alive [NUMBER]) (None2, DontKnow, Refusal)
How many of your grandparents are alive?
NUMBER [0..10]

IF ((age > 40)AND(BKIDS.nkidstotal > 0))

○

b11GEN55 (Has grandchild) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you have any grandchildren?

Yes

No

IF (b11GEN55 = yes)

▪

b11GEN56 (Grandchildren [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How many grandchildren do you have?

NUMBER [1..99]

ENDIF

ENDIF

LEAVING AND RETURNING TO THE PARENTAL HOME

b11PAR10 (Living with parent(s) at W1) (DontKnow, Refusal)

At the time of the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), did you live in the same household as at least one of your parents? In this question and the following questions parents include biological, step, adoptive and foster parents.

Yes

No

IF (((b11PAR10 = no)AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.mumcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.dadcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = no))

○

b11PAR11A (Reasons for first moving out of parental home) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Why did you first stop living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxPar11a[1] := 'I went to college or university'

auxPar11a[2] := 'I started a job or apprenticeship'

auxPar11a[3] := 'I went travelling'

auxPar11a[4] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'

auxPar11a[5] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'

auxPar11a[6] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'

auxPar11a[7] := 'I had a child/ became pregnant'

auxPar11a[8] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'

auxPar11a[9] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'

auxPar11a[10] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR11A) > 1)

▪

b11PAR11B (Main reason for first moving out of parental home) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you first stopped living with your parent(s)?

auxPar11a[1] := 'I went to college or university'

auxPar11a[2] := 'I started a job or apprenticeship'

auxPar11a[3] := 'I went travelling'
auxPar11a[4] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'
auxPar11a[5] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'
auxPar11a[6] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'
auxPar11a[7] := 'I had a child/ became pregnant'
auxPar11a[8] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'
auxPar11a[9] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'
auxPar11a[10] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF (((b11PAR10 = yes)AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.mumcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.dadcores = no))AND(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = no))

○

b11PAR12A (Reasons for moving out of parental home between W1 and W2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

You said you were living with at least one biological/step/adoptive/foster parent at the time of the last survey, but now you are not. Why aren't you living with them anymore? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxMoveReason2[1] := 'I went to college or university'
auxMoveReason2[2] := 'I left to start a job or apprenticeship'
auxMoveReason2[3] := 'I left to look for a (better) job'
auxMoveReason2[4] := 'I went travelling'
auxMoveReason2[5] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'
auxMoveReason2[6] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'
auxMoveReason2[7] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'
auxMoveReason2[8] := 'I had a child /became pregnant'
auxMoveReason2[9] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'
auxMoveReason2[10] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'
auxMoveReason2[11] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR12A) > 1)

▪

b11PAR12B (Main reason for moving out of parental home between W1 and w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you moved out?

auxMoveReason2[1] := 'I went to college or university'
auxMoveReason2[2] := 'I left to start a job or apprenticeship'
auxMoveReason2[3] := 'I left to look for a (better) job'

auxMoveReason2[4] := 'I went travelling'

auxMoveReason2[5] := 'I got married or started to live with my partner'

auxMoveReason2[6] := 'I wanted to live on my own or with friends'

auxMoveReason2[7] := 'I fell out with my parent(s)/they asked me to leave'

auxMoveReason2[8] := 'I had a child /became pregnant'

auxMoveReason2[9] := 'My parents' home was overcrowded'

auxMoveReason2[10] := 'My parent(s) moved out or died'

auxMoveReason2[11] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((b11PAR10 = yes)AND(((BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.mumcores = yes)OR(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.dadcores = yes))OR(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = yes)))

○

b11PAR13A (*Reasons for still living in parental home*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

What are the reasons you are living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxStayReason[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'

auxStayReason[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'

auxStayReason[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'

auxStayReason[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'

auxStayReason[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'

auxStayReason[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'

auxStayReason[9] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR13A) > 1)

▪

b11PAR13B (*Main reason for still living in parental home*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

What is the most important reason you are living with your parent(s)?

auxStayReason[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'

auxStayReason[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'

auxStayReason[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'
auxStayReason[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'
auxStayReason[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'
auxStayReason[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'
auxStayReason[9] := 'Other'

ENDIF

ENDIF

IF ((b11PAR10 = no)AND(((BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.mumcores = yes)OR(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.dadcores = yes))OR(BHOUSEHOLDMEMBERS.adopt_step_fosterparentcores = yes)))

○

b11PAR14A (Reasons for moving back to the parental home in W2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the reason you are living with your parent(s)? Please choose all that apply to you.

SET OF

auxStayReason2[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason2[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason2[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'

auxStayReason2[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'

auxStayReason2[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'

auxStayReason2[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'

auxStayReason2[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'

auxStayReason2[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'

auxStayReason2[9] := 'I broke up with partner/spouse'

auxStayReason2[10] := 'I became unemployed'

auxStayReason2[11] := 'My studies came to an end'

auxStayReason2[12] := 'I returned from travelling'

auxStayReason2[13] := 'The accommodation I was living in is no longer available'

auxStayReason2[14] := 'Other'

IF (count(b11PAR14A) > 1)

▪

b11PAR14B (Main reason for moving back to the parental home in w2) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the main reason you are currently living with your parent(s)?

auxStayReason2[1] := 'Currently I cannot afford to live away from my parent(s)'

auxStayReason2[2] := 'To save money first so that I can afford to buy or rent my own home'

auxStayReason2[3] := 'It's more convenient for work/study'
auxStayReason2[4] := 'I'm happy to live with my parents'
auxStayReason2[5] := 'I don't feel ready to leave'
auxStayReason2[6] := 'My parent(s) don't want me to move out at the moment'
auxStayReason2[7] := 'My parent's/parents' health'
auxStayReason2[8] := 'My partner's, my child(ren)'s, or my own health'
auxStayReason2[9] := 'I broke up with partner/spouse'
auxStayReason2[10] := 'I became unemployed'
auxStayReason2[11] := 'My studies came to an end'
auxStayReason2[12] := 'I returned from travelling'
auxStayReason2[13] := 'The accommodation I was living in is no longer available'
auxStayReason2[14] := 'Other'

ENDIF
ENDIF

INTENSIVE PARENTING

INTintro (*Intensive parenting Intro*) (*Empty*)

The next section will ask general questions about your views on parenting nowadays. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with these statements.

b12INT01A (*Intensive parenting: Mental strain*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Parents never get a mental break from their children, even when they are physically apart
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b12INT01B (*Intensive Parenting: Children in stimulating activities*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Beyond regular school classes it is important for children to be involved in classes, lessons, and activities that engage and stimulate them
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree
Agree
Strongly agree

b12INT01C (*Intensive parenting: Demanding job*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Childrearing is a really demanding job
Strongly disagree
Disagree
Neither agree nor disagree

Agree
Strongly agree

b12INT01D (*Intensive parenting: Attention*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Children should be the center of their parents' attention

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01E (*Intensive parenting: Educational opportunities*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Finding the best educational opportunities for children is important even before they go to school

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01F (*Intensive parenting: Child's needs first*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Children's needs should come before their parents

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01G (*Intensive parenting: No alone time*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Being a parent means never having time for oneself

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01H (*Intensive parenting: Prioritise child's schedule*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The child's schedule should take priority over the needs of the parents

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

b12INT01I (*Intensive parenting: Interacting with children*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

It is important to interact regularly with children on their level (e.g., getting down on the floor and playing with them)

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

EDUCATION AND WORK

ECRINT (*ERC Intro*) (*Empty*)

In this section, we would like to find out more about your daily activities and work.

b13ECR01 (Increased educational level) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Since the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), have you completed any new (higher) level of education?

Yes

No

IF (b13ECR01 = yes)

◻

◦ **b13DEM07** (Educational level) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Please select the education level that corresponds most closely to the highest level of education you have completed.

Early childhood education

Primary education

Lower secondary education

Upper secondary education

Post-secondary non tertiary education

Short cycle tertiary education

Bachelor or equivalent

Master or equivalent

Doctoral or equivalent

b13DEM08 (ECR03_intro) (Empty)

When did you reach that level?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b13DEM08Y (Year education reached) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b13DEM08Y = DontKnow)OR(b13DEM08Y = Refusal)))

▪ ◻

b13DEM08M (Month education reached) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b13DEM08Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b13DEM08Y = DontKnow))OR(b13DEM08Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

b13DEM06 (Activity status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Which of the items best describes your current employment status?

If you are evenly split between two or more of these activities, select the one which you feel best describes your current situation.

In education or training
Employed
Self-employed
Helping family member in a family farm or business
Unemployed
Retired
In military or civic service
On maternity or paternity leave
On parental leave or childcare leave
Taking care of the home or family
Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
Other

IF (NOT(((b13DEM06 = 2)OR(b13DEM06 = DontKnow))OR(b13DEM06 = Refusal))))

○

b13WRK03 (ECR05a_ intro) (Empty)

When did this period of ^b13DEM06; begin?

If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b13WRK03Y (Date starting status YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year

YYYY

Vertical

NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b13WRK03Y = DontKnow)OR(b13WRK03Y = Refusal)))

▪

b13WRK03M (Date starting status MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)

month

January

February

March

April

May

June

July

August

September

October

November

December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b13WRK03Y >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b13WRK03Y = DontKnow))OR(b13WRK03Y = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

IF (((b13DEM06 = 2)OR(b13DEM06 = 8))OR(b13DEM06 = 9))

○

b13ECR05B (ECR05b_ intro) (Empty)

When did your employment begin?

Please indicate since when you are continuously employed, even if you might have changed position or employer during this time. If you are unsure of the precise date, please provide your best estimate.

b13ECR05BY (Date starting employment YEAR) (DontKnow, Refusal)

year
YYYY
Vertical
NUMBER [1900..2030]

IF (NOT((b13ECR05BY = DontKnow)OR(b13ECR05BY = Refusal)))

- **b13ECR05BM** (Date starting employment MONTH) (DontKnow, Refusal)
 - month
 - January
 - February
 - March
 - April
 - May
 - June
 - July
 - August
 - September
 - October
 - November
 - December

ENDIF

CHECK: (((b13ECR05BY >= BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)OR(b13ECR05BY = DontKnow))OR(b13ECR05BY = Refusal)) [Not possible to enter a year before your birth year TOSTRING(BDEMOGRAPHICS.b1DEM02Y)]

ENDIF

b13ECR06 (Other employment changes) (nota, DontKnow, Refusal)

Apart from your current situation, was there a period since the last survey (^auxFirstWaveMonthYear;), when you experienced the following situations for at least 3 months? Please, mark all that apply.

SET OF In education or training

Employed

Self-employed

Helping family member in a family farm or business

Unemployed

Retired

In military or civic service

On maternity or paternity leave

On parental leave or childcare leave

Taking care of the home or family

Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

Other

b13WRK02 (Employment status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Have you been in paid work in the last week?

In paid work refers to someone who either:

a) worked for pay, profit or family gain for at least one hour in the last week or;

b) were not at work during the last week but has a job or business from which they were temporarily absent (i.e. on holiday or some form of leave)

In paid work (worked for pay, profit or family gain at least one hour)

In paid work but on temporary leave or holiday

Not in paid work, but looking for work

Not in paid work and not looking for work

- IF ((b13WRK02 = 1)OR(b13WRK02 = 2))

○

b13WRK06 (*Work time*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Is your work full time or part time?

Full time

Part time

b13WRK07 (*Hours worked per week*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How many hours per week do you normally work in this job or business including overtime?

NUMBER [0..140]

b13ECR10 (*Home office*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Thinking about the last four weeks, did you do work any full work days at home?

Yes

No, my type of work does not allow it

No, although my type of work would allow it

IF (b13ECR10 = 1)

▪

b13ECR11 (*Home office days [NUMBER]*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Altogether, about how many days did you work at home during the last four weeks?

NUMBER [0..31]

ENDIF

b13WRK11 (*Evening work*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Thinking about the last four weeks, did you ever work for at least 2 hours in the evening or at night (between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.)?

Yes, twice or more per week

Yes, less than twice per week

No

b13WRK13 (*Weekend work*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Thinking of the last four weeks, did you work on Saturdays or Sundays?

Yes, twice or more in the last four weeks

Yes, less than twice in the last four weeks

No

b13WRK16A (*Likelihood of job loss in 12m*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

How likely is it that you will lose your job in the next twelve months?

Very unlikely

Unlikely

Unsure

Likely

Very likely

IF (NOT(b13DEM06 = 3))

▪

b13WRK18 (*Current contract type*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Is your current work contract, if you have any, a permanent contract, a fixed term contract, or a temporary contract?

Permanent

Fixed term

Temporary

No written contract

b13WRK20 (*Flexible work arrangements*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Does your employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to children's schedules?

Yes
No

ENDIF

ENDIF

b13ATT11B (Ideal work hours for mothers) (Notall, DontKnow, Refusal)

Consider a family with a mother, father and a two-year-old child. How many hours a week should the mother work?

Vertical

NUMBER [0..99]

b13ATT11D (Ideal work hours for fathers) (Notall, DontKnow, Refusal)

Consider a family with a mother, father and a two-year old child. How many hours a week should the father work?

Vertical

NUMBER [0..99]

IF (haspartner = yes)

○

EDUCATION AND WORK OF PARTNER

ECPINT (ECON_PARTNER: Intro) (Empty)

The next questions are about your partner's present work and daily activities.

b14DEM25 (Partners education level) (DontKnow, Refusal)

What is the highest level of education your partner has successfully completed?

Please select the education level that corresponds most closely to the highest level of education he/she has completed.

Early childhood education

Primary education

Lower secondary education

Upper secondary education

Post-secondary non tertiary education

Short cycle tertiary education

Bachelor or equivalent

Master or equivalent

Doctoral or equivalent

b14DEM26 (Partners employment status) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Which of the items best describes your partner's current employment status?

If they are evenly split between two or more of these activities, select the one which you feel best describes their current situation.

In education or training

Employed

Self-employed

Helping family member in a family farm or business

Unemployed

Retired

In military or civic service

On maternity or paternity leave

On parental leave or childcare leave

Taking care of the home or family

Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently

Other

b14ECP03 (Partners other employment changes) (Nota, DontKnow, Refusal)
Apart from your partner's current situation, was there a period in the last three years, when your partner experienced the following situations for at least 3 months? Please, mark all that apply.

SET OF In education or training
Employed
Self-employed
Helping family member in a family farm or business
Unemployed
Retired
In military or civic service
On maternity or paternity leave
On parental leave or childcare leave
Taking care of the home or family
Ill or disabled for a long time or permanently
Other

b14WRK32 (Partners activity status) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Has your partner been in paid work during the last week?
In paid work (worked for pay, profit or family gain at least one hour)
In paid work but on temporary leave or holiday
Not in paid work, but looking for work
Not in paid work and not looking for work

IF ((b14WRK32 = 1)OR(b14WRK32 = 2))

▪
b14WRK35 (Partners work hours) (DontKnow, Refusal)
How many hours per week does your partner normally work in this job or business including overtime?
NUMBER [0..140]

b14ECP06 (Home office) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Thinking about the last four weeks, did your partner work any full work days at home?
Yes
No, my partner's type of work does not allow it
No, although my partner's type of work would allow it

IF (b14ECP06 = 1)

▪
b14ECP07 (Home office days [NUMBER]) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Altogether, about how many days did your partner work at home during the last four weeks?
NUMBER [0..31]

ENDIF

b14WRK38 (Partner works in the evening) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Thinking about the last four weeks, did your partner work for at least 2 hours in the evening or at night (between 8 p.m. and 5 a.m.)?
Yes, twice or more per week
Yes, less than twice per week
No

b14WRK40 (Partner works weekends) (DontKnow, Refusal)
Thinking of the last four weeks, did your partner work on Saturdays or Sundays?

Yes, twice or more in the last four weeks
Yes, less than twice in the last four weeks
No

b14WRK42 (Partners likelihood of job loss in 12m) (DontKnow, Refusal)

How likely is it that your partner will lose their job in the next twelve months?

Very unlikely
Unlikely
Unsure
Likely
Very likely

IF (NOT(b14DEM26 = 3))

▪

b14WRK44 (Partners current contract type) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Is your partner's current work contract, if any, a permanent contract, a fixed term contract, or a temporary contract?

Permanent
Fixed term
Temporary
No written contract

b14WRK46 (Partner has flexible work arrangements) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Does your partner's employer allow regular flexible time arrangements for personal reasons, like for adapting to childrens schedules?

Yes
No

ENDIF

ENDIF

ENDIF

FINANCIAL SITUATION

b15MAT00 (MAT intro) (Empty)

The next couple of questions are about the financial situation of your household.

b15INC03 (Can make ends meet) (DontKnow, Refusal)

A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...

With great difficulty
With difficulty
With some difficulty
Fairly easily
Easily
Very easily

b15INC06 (Total Household Net Income) (DontKnow, Refusal)

If you add up the income from all sources received during the last 12 months, what is your household total net income from all members including yourself? Please state the net income, which means after deductions for taxes and social security.

4,999 € or less
5,000 to 9,999 €
10,000 to 19,999 €
20,000 to 39,999 €
40,000 to 59,999 €
60,000 to 79,999 €
80,000 to 99,999 €
100,000 € or more

b15INC12 (Income in 3 years) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Do you think that your financial situation will get better or worse or will be about the same in three years from now?

Much better
Better
Neither better nor worse
Worse
Much worse

IF (hascorespartner = yes)

○

b15MAT04 (Higher income) (DontKnow, Refusal)

In an average month, who has the higher personal income – you or your partner?

I earn more
My partner earns more
We earn about the same

ENDIF

GLOBAL UNCERTAINTY

UNCintro (Uncertainty intro) (Empty)

We would like to ask you some questions on how you perceive the world around you.

b16UNC01 (Unc01 intro) (Empty)

Thinking about the future, how much does the following worry you?

b16UNC01A (Worried: Terrorism) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Terrorism
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01B (Worried: Climate change) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Climate change
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01C (Worried: Overpopulation) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Overpopulation
Very worrying
Somewhat worrying
Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01D (Worried: Economic crisis) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Economic crises

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01E (Worried: Increased number of refugees) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Increased number of refugees

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01F (Worried: High unemployment) (DontKnow, Refusal)

High unemployment

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01G (Worried: Organised crime) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Organised crime

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01H (Worried: Military conflicts) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Military conflicts

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01I (Worried: Global epidemics) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Global epidemics

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01J (Worried: Weakened democracy) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Weakened democracy

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01K (Worried: Increased social inequality) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Increased social inequality

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC01L (Worried: Political extremism) (DontKnow, Refusal)

Political extremism

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying
Not at all worrying

b16UNC01M (*Worried: Future generations' prospect*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Prospect of future generations

Very worrying

Somewhat worrying

Not particularly worrying

Not at all worrying

b16UNC02 (*b16UNC02 intro*) (*Empty*)

The next questions ask your opinion about different institutions in 18;

How much confidence do you have in the way the following institutions and groups do their job?

b16UNC02A (*Trust: The government*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The government

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02B (*Trust: The police*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The police

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02C (*Trust: Medical services*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Medical services

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02D (*Trust: The civil service*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The civil service

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02E (*Trust: News media*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

News media

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

Quite low trust

Very low trust

b16UNC02F (*Trust: The EU*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

The EU

Very high trust

Quite high trust

Neither high nor low trust

*Quite low trust
Very low trust*

b16ATT01 (*General trust*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Generally speaking, would you say that most people can be trusted or that you need to be very careful in dealing with people?

*Most people can be trusted
Need to be very careful*

b16UNC03B (*Perception of honesty and fairness*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Do you think that most people would try to take advantage of you if they got a chance or would they try to be honest and fair?

*Would take advantage
Would try to be honest and fair*

b16UNC04 (*Optimism*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Optimists are people who look to the future with confidence and who mostly expect good things to happen. How would you describe yourself? How optimistic are you in general? Please express your opinion on a scale of 1 to 5.

1 Not at all optimistic

2

3

4

5 Very optimistic

b16UNC05 (*Risk aversion*) (*DontKnow, Refusal*)

Would you describe yourself as someone who tries to avoid risk (risk averse) or someone who likes to take chances (a risk taker)?

Please express your opinion on a scale of 1 to 5.

1 Risk averse

2

3

4

5 Risktaker

thanks

Many thanks for your participation in the survey, we greatly appreciate your time. If you have any questions about the survey or would like further information, you can contact us on [TELEPHONE NUMBER] or by emailing [EMAIL ADDRESS].

End interview